

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: O'BRIEN****FIRST NAME: ARCHILENE****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Professor Gulma**

The author applied X UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author X did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 3%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. According to Turabian, what should a writer achieve with their research questions?
 - To find answers to essential issues that add value to the field, reader, and topic.¹**
 - To ensure the issue is objective and logical
 - To ensure a rich supply of data from credible sources
 - To ensure a well-structured case for the argument.
2. How does Turabian suggest understanding research problems?
 - By focusing on the research question, the methodology, and the expected results.

¹ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers* (Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018), 22.

- By highlighting the research objectives, the data analysis, and the practical implications
 - By emphasizing the research topic, the literature review, and the theoretical framework.
 - By stating what you are working on, what you want to find out, and how it will impact the reader.²**
3. A college student, Alex, finishes a draft of an essay late at night. Feeling exhausted, he takes a break and returns to it the next day. Upon reviewing his work in the morning, he realizes some ideas are unclear and needs modification for better flow. He reflects on his arguments and considers how to enhance clarity before submitting. How can Alex improve the clarity of his ideas during revision?
- By adding more complex vocabulary to impress the reader.
 - By restructuring sentences and ensuring logical connections between points.³**
 - By focusing solely on grammar and punctuation corrections.
 - By removing all personal opinions to maintain objectivity.
4. What are the five academic research goals outlined by Turabian?
- Answering important questions that add value, ensuring the issue is subjective and emotional, using credible data to support reasoning, constructing a case for the argument, and revisiting all steps to meet targets.

² Ibid., 28.

³ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 17.

- Answering important questions that add value, ensuring the issue is objective and logical, using credible data to support reasoning, constructing a case for the argument, and revisiting all steps to meet targets.**⁴
 - Answering important questions that add value, ensuring the issue is objective and logical, using credible data to support reasoning, constructing a case for the argument, and ignoring the need to revisit all steps.
 - Answering important questions that add value, ensuring the issue is objective and logical, using credible data to support reasoning, constructing a case for the argument, and focusing solely on data collection
5. What are the four reasons for citing sources according to Turabian?
- To pay tribute to the researcher, to validate information for the reader, to provide a more comprehensive perspective for the reader, and to enlarge the library of credible resources.**⁵
 - To acknowledge the researcher, to verify data accuracy, to offer a broader viewpoint, and to expand the collection of reliable sources.
 - To honour the author, to confirm information validity, to present a broader context, and to increase the pool of trustworthy references.
 - To credit the originator, to ensure data reliability, to enrich the reader's understanding, and to enhance the repository of credible materials.

⁴ Ibid., 22.

⁵ Ibid., 139.

6. A graduate student, April, struggles with citing resources correctly. What questions can help guide her in fulfilling the information citation requirement?
- What is the source's title, and who created it? Who are the publishers, and when was the source published? What is the source's abstract?
 - What is the source's title, and who created it? Who are the publishers, and when was the source published? What is the source's ISBN?
 - What is the source's title, and who created it? Who are the publishers, and when was the source published? Where could the source be found?⁶**
 - What is the source's title, and who created it? Who are the publishers, and when was the source published? What is the source's DOI?
7. What are some examples of citation management tools mentioned in the text?
- Paperpile
 - Mendeley
 - Citations
 - Endnotes, RefWorks, and Zotero.⁷**
8. What role do citation management tools play in research?
- They enhance the visual appeal of citations by formatting them in a uniform style.
 - They improve the accessibility of research data by providing a centralized repository.

⁶ Ibid., 141.

⁷ Ibid., 140.

- They facilitate collaborative research by sharing citation information among team members.
- They facilitate collaborative research by sharing citation information among team members.⁸**

9. A graduate student, Brandon, is preparing his qualitative dissertation and has identified several frequent errors in methodology. He is concerned about incorrect citations, limited resource depth, and excluding contradictory literature. Brandon seeks to improve his research quality by addressing these issues effectively. Why is it problematic to exclude contradictory literature in research?

- It allows researchers to focus solely on supportive evidence.
- It creates bias and weakens the argument's overall balance.⁹**
- It ensures that only strong arguments are presented in the study.
- It simplifies the writing process for the researcher significantly.

10. What is the significance of understanding both qualitative and quantitative research methods?

- It enables researchers to concentrate exclusively on subjective, experiential insights.
- It allows researchers to focus solely on objective, numerical data.
- It permits researchers to rely solely on statistical analysis.

⁸ Ibid.

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publication, 2019), 79.

- It allows researchers to integrate objective data with subjective experiences.¹⁰

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Adu, Philip. *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*. YouTube, 2016.
- Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. 4th ed. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 3rd ed. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.
- Turabian, Katie L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph Bizup, William T. Fitzgerald, University of Chicago Press Editorial Staff. 9th ed. Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ Philip Adu, "Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study," *YouTube*, March 6, 2016, video, 1:05:16, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=KRHvxY3N708&t=2643s>.